

OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PULPITIS OF PERMANENT TEETH IN ELDERLY AGES

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ABSTRACT

The main priority in the treatment of caries complications in permanent teeth with immature roots is to keep the pulp viable to complete apexogenesis . Treatment of pulpitis of a permanent tooth, the roots of which are at the stage of formation, presents objective difficulties for a dentist. The anatomical features of unformed roots, such as thin root walls, a bell in the apical part of the root, which passes into the growth zone, make endodontic manipulations technically difficult. Treatment of permanent teeth with a formed root in children also involves maintaining the vitality of the pulp for the longest possible time. This is achieved by using conservative methods for treating pulpitis. It has been proven that endodontically treated teeth have lower survival rates, in some cases they are latent, and under certain conditions, active foci of infection and intoxication. With the development of clinical dentistry, materials that help preserve the vitality of all or part of the pulp, and methods of their use in teeth with immature roots in children, are constantly being studied and improved.

Introduction . Currently, pediatric dentists use several groups of materials for pulp therapy, but they have some disadvantages. Materials based on calcium hydroxide have been used in clinical practice for a long time. This drug promotes pulp regeneration and induces the production of replacement dentin, but has a number of disadvantages, such as material resorption, mechanical instability and instability to microleakage over a long period of time. The formation of "tunnel defects" in the formed mineralized barriers facilitates the penetration of microorganisms, which can cause a secondary inflammatory process in the pulp tissues.. In modern clinical practice, new bioactive materials based on mineral trioxide aggregate and tricalcium silicate are being introduced, showing promising clinical results, however, more detailed studies and longer periods are required for final conclusions observations. The literature available to us contains detailed studies of dental status and descriptions of various methods of treating pulpitis using bioactive

materials with assessment of changes in microcirculation in the pulp in adult patients. At the same time, in domestic and foreign sources we were unable to find systematic data on the use of bioactive materials in the treatment of pulpitis of immature teeth, the effect on changes in microcirculation in the dental pulp in childhood and the success of treatment in general.

Purpose of the work : Increasing the effectiveness of treatment of complicated forms of caries in permanent teeth in children through the use of modern bioactive materials.

Research materials. 50 patients, of which x in boys averages x 56 %, 44%. girls

Research methods. 1) laboratory research methods , 2) clinical method (X-ray examination , Doppler ultrasound) 3) statistical data processing

Results. It is substantiated that the use of materials based on tricalcium silicate " Vuyoepipe " and based on oxides of calcium, silicon and aluminum " Trioxident " in the treatment of initial pulpitis of permanent teeth with unformed roots makes it possible to complete the process of apexogenesis in physiological terms. When using these bioactive materials in all cases of treating teeth with unformed and formed roots, the vitality of the pulp is preserved. that the use of materials based on tricalcium silicate " Vuyoepipe " and based on oxides of calcium, silicon and aluminum " Trioxident " in the treatment of initial pulpitis of permanent teeth with unformed roots makes it possible to complete the process of apexogenesis in physiological terms. When using these bioactive materials in all cases of treating teeth with unformed and formed roots, the vitality of the pulp is preserved.

Conclusions _ In the treatment of complicated caries (direct covering of the dental pulp) with a material based on tricalcium silicate " Vuyoepipe ", a more pronounced deposition of replacement dentin was observed in the long term (up to 24 months after treatment) compared to a material based on calcium, silicon and aluminum oxides " Trioxident ". It has been established that activation of replacement dentin deposition during direct dental pulp coating occurs 18-24 months after treatment.

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